

INTERNATIONAL CREDIT RELATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN AND ITS ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF FOREIGN ECONOMIC RELATIONS

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Abstract: This article covers different approaches to determining creditworthiness in different countries and their main goal is the effective use of bank loans.

Key words: international credit, finance, world economy, currency relations, securities.

International credit - loans given by states, banks, firms, individuals and legal entities of one country to the governments, banks, firms of other countries, as well as the movement of money and material means in international economic relations, is closely related to the emergence and development of the world economy. The principles (principles) of international credit reveal its economic nature more deeply.

The relationship between international credit and reproduction can be seen in the following main principles:

A) repayability: an international loan must be repaid within an agreed period, like a domestic loan. If received funds if not returned, then to the nature of transfer of non-refundable money capital has the form of financing.

B) term: within the terms specified in the loan agreement ensures repayment of the loan.

C) solvency: apply the law of value and credit differential represents ways of implementing the conditions and for international credit the paid interest is the price of this loan.

D) financial security: arising from a loan means a guarantee of repayment of the loan against risks.

E) goal orientation: specific objects of the loan to determine, the main purpose of its application is the creditor state to stimulate export.

Functions of international credit International credit performs the following functions reflecting the circulation of loan capital within international economic relations:

1. In order to meet the needs of expanded production distribution of loan capital between countries. International credit loan capital through the mechanism of economic in order to ensure profit agents are directed to the desired areas. Through this, the credit is national to turn profit into average profit and increase its mass will help.

2. Real money (gold and silver) in international accounts exchange of credit with money, as well as non-cash payments Acceleration and development of cash and currency transactions, international credit Exchange transactions save transaction costs.

Credit instruments of international settlements on the basis of international loans

- promissory note, check, as well as bank transfers, deposit certificates and others were created. International economic economy of time of transaction of loan capital in relations at the expense of increasing the time of the production function of capital it is possible to expand output and increase profits.

3. Acceleration of accumulation and centralization of capital. Abroad capitalization of additional value at the expense of attracting loans accelerates, the boundaries of individual accumulation expand, one country entrepreneurs' capital at the expense of other countries' funds will increase. Credit to other countries within certain limits gives the opportunity to own capital, labor and property. Privileged foreign lending to large companies and small and the possibility of entering the

world loan capital market of a medium-sized company reduction is causing the accumulation and centralization of capital.¹

- Depending on whether the loan funds are assigned to a foreign economic transaction is divided into:
 - commercial loans - direct with foreign trade and services connected;
 - financial loans - used for any purpose, that's it including proper capital investments, construction of investment facilities, purchase of valuable securities, payment of foreign debt, currency intervention.
 - intermediate loans - capital, production of goods and services assigned to serve mixed forms, for example, contract in the form of doing work. Loans according to their appearance are divided into goods
 - - mainly given by exporters to buyers and foreign currency - loans given by banks in the form of money.

There are 2 forms of international credit:

1. International bank loan;
2. International commercial credit.

International bank credit is mainly in the form of currency (money). International commercial credit usually takes the form of goods.

There are several types of loans that stem from these 2 main types of loans:

1. Company (commercial) credit - usually a company from an exporting country delays payment to an importer from another country

It is understood that he gives a loan in the form of Commercial credit in foreign trade widely used in calculations related to commodity operations. Commerce The term of the loan (usually 2-7 years) varies.

¹ International currency-credit relations: Textbook / T.I. Bobakulov, U.A. Abdullayev; - T.: "Economy-Finance", 2019. — 228 p.

2. In promissory credit, the exporter concludes an agreement on the sale of goods, sends a bill of exchange (draft) to the importer, the importer is commercial accepts the documents, that is, the payment within the period specified in it agrees to the implementation.

3. Credit given on open accounts. This is a credit exporter and based on the agreement between the importer. Exporter sent recording the value of each commodity as a credit to the import account goes The importer will pay the loan amount at the time specified in the contract will pay. Loans on open accounts only implementation only between companies that are in constant contact Possible Bank credit - in the form of a loan for crediting exports and imports appears and it is goods, goods documents, bills of exchange and is given as collateral. Sometimes banks themselves blank loan to closely related large exporting companies, that is, they provide loans without formal guarantees. Export credit - delivery of the exporter's bank to the importer's bank given machine, equipment and other investments it is said to credit goods. Bank loans are given in the form of money and have the character of "dependency", because the borrower is given a loan only for the purchase of goods of the creditor country.

International credit is characterized by the following features:
the state, organization and as a borrower and lender institutions, legal entities, international currency credit organizations participate;

- borrowed funds by the borrowing country used as income generating capital;
- source of loan interest paid to the lending country national income generated by the population of the borrowing country is;
- agreed loan price;
- hidden elements of credit assessment.

Insurance premium is paid to special insurance institutions.

Because they have the obligation to cover possible losses within the agreed amount with the insurer.

undertake. Currently, export credit insurance the amount to make is 80-90% of the possible losses, and sometimes even 100%.

International credit is not returned on time banks. Negative about the activities of international financial institutions created the impression.

In 1982, the Argentine government declared itself in default and guarantee for international loans attracted to the country Inability to fulfill obligations, debt due to international loans showed that the problem has reached its climax. This Until then, there was no problem of bankruptcy of the government.

The emergence of the problem of indebtedness on international loans explained by the following reasons:

1. Economic in countries that attract international credit deterioration of business conditions.
2. A sharp decrease in the value of the national currency.

In Mexico, in 1982, the value of the national currency, the peso, was sharply increased International credit received in US dollars as a result of the decrease it was not possible to return it.

There is a sharp decline in the value of the national currency in Uzbekistan observed at the time when the national currency was put into circulation (July 1994) in the first currency trade, the soum is nominal against 1 US dollar the exchange rate was 7.00 soums. By April 2023 came, and its exchange rate exceeded 11,460.00 soums.²

Depreciation of the national currency at such a high rate led to an increase in import prices. The increase in the price of imports in turn, it caused the increase of inflation.

² nbu.uz/uz/exchange-rates/

Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 22, 2001 No. 263 of the Court "Further liberalization of the currency market the adoption of the decision on measures" national currency increase the liquidity of the market, the supply of foreign currencies is significant it became a serious reality from the point of view of increasing the level.³

On September 2, 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed the Decree "On the first measures to liberalize the currency policy" as another proof of practical measures to liberalize the currency market. In the document, the priorities of the state economic policy in the field of foreign exchange market liberalization in Uzbekistan were defined.

From September 5, 2017, Uzbekistan began to freely buy foreign currency from individuals.⁴

The credit system of each country includes central and commercial banks, non-banking and other organizations. In particular, the State Bank of Switzerland controls the activities of about 40 commercial banks, and there are about 13,000 commercial banks in the United States. In Switzerland, there is one financial institution for every 10,000 inhabitants, in Russia there are 2,486 commercial banks licensed by the Central Bank at the beginning of 1995.

In all countries, it is important to assess the customer's creditworthiness in credit relations.

³ Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 263 of June 22, 2001 "On measures to further liberalize the currency market". 0 Financial laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent, 2001. - #8. - B. 26.

⁴ Decree of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on September 2, 2017 "On the first measures to liberalize the currency policy".

11 countries with AAA credit ratings from S&P in 2021

1. Germany
 2. Australia
 3. Canada
 4. Switzerland
 5. Denmark
 6. Liechtenstein
 7. Luxembourg
 8. Netherlands
 9. Norway
 10. Sweden
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In particular, in the USA, the 5 "S" method is used to assess the creditworthiness of the client and minimize the credit risk. This method includes the following criteria for evaluating the client's activity.

1. Customer reputation
2. Solvency
3. Amount of capital
4. Credit security
5. Economic situation and its future.

Based on the above, in conclusion, despite the fact that there are different approaches to determining creditworthiness in different countries, their main goal is to ensure the effective use of loans given by the bank and their timely return to the bank.

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